

Comparative Study of Financial Derivatives Usage in Indian vs. Global Markets

Dr Suraksha Sharma, Lecturer- Department of Accountancy and Business Statistics, B.B.D Government College, Chimanpura, Shahpura, District- Jaipur (Rajasthan)

Abstract

This research paper presents a comparative study of financial derivatives usage in Indian and global markets, examining their roles in enhancing market efficiency, liquidity, and risk management. The paper analyzes key differences and similarities between these markets, focusing on market size, types of derivatives traded, regulatory frameworks, and their impact on market efficiency. Global markets, with a notional value of \$544 trillion, demonstrate a broader scope and higher trading volumes compared to the Indian market, which had a turnover of ₹259 trillion. The study highlights how derivatives contribute to price discovery, improve liquidity, and aid in risk management, using quantitative data and qualitative insights. Despite these benefits, the paper also addresses challenges such as systemic risk, market volatility, and regulatory concerns. The findings underscore the need for robust regulatory frameworks and effective risk management practices to mitigate potential drawbacks and enhance market stability. This comparative analysis provides valuable insights into how derivatives markets operate across different economic contexts and identifies areas for growth and improvement in the Indian derivatives market.

Keywords: Financial derivatives, market efficiency, systemic risk, liquidity, price discovery, regulatory frameworks, Indian derivatives market, global derivatives market, risk management, market volatility

1. Introduction

Financial derivatives have become essential instruments in modern financial markets, offering mechanisms for risk management, speculation, and arbitrage (Black & Scholes, 1973). These financial contracts derive their value from an underlying asset, such as stocks, bonds, commodities, or currencies. By enabling parties to hedge against price movements or speculate on future price changes, derivatives contribute significantly to market efficiency and liquidity (Hull, 2015).

In recent decades, the global derivatives market has witnessed substantial growth. As of 2016, the notional value of outstanding derivatives globally was approximately \$544 trillion, reflecting a sharp increase from \$95 trillion in 2000 (Bank for International Settlements [BIS], 2016). This growth underscores the integral role of derivatives in the financial ecosystem.

India, a rapidly emerging market, has also seen considerable development in its derivatives market. The National Stock Exchange (NSE) and the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) offer various derivatives products, including equity futures and options, index futures, and currency futures (NSE India, 2016). As of 2016, the total turnover in the Indian derivatives market was around ₹259 trillion, marking a significant rise from ₹35 trillion in 2010 (Securities and Exchange Board of India [SEBI], 2016). This increase indicates the growing acceptance and usage of derivatives among Indian investors and institutions.

The importance of comparing the derivatives usage in Indian markets with that in global markets lies in understanding the differences in market structures, regulatory environments, and usage patterns. Such a comparative study can provide insights into how Indian markets align with or diverge from global practices, thereby highlighting potential areas for growth and improvement (Jones, 2016).

This study aims to offer a comprehensive comparative analysis of derivatives usage in Indian versus global markets, exploring key differences and similarities in market dynamics, regulatory frameworks, and trading practices. By leveraging qualitative insights and quantitative data, this research seeks to enhance understanding of the role and evolution of financial derivatives in different economic contexts.

2. Literature Review

The development and utilization of financial derivatives have been extensively studied in financial literature, reflecting their critical role in modern markets. Financial derivatives emerged prominently in the 1970s, marked by the introduction of the Black-Scholes model for option pricing, which revolutionized financial theory and practice (Black & Scholes, 1973). This model laid the groundwork for the quantitative approach to pricing derivatives and managing risk.

In the decades following, the derivatives market expanded rapidly, driven by innovations in financial instruments and trading strategies. By the early 2000s, the global derivatives market had become a cornerstone of financial trading, with the notional value of outstanding derivatives reaching \$350 trillion by 2007 (Bank for International Settlements [BIS], 2016). This growth was propelled by increased market participation, financial globalization, and advancements in technology.

The academic literature has highlighted various aspects of derivatives usage, including risk management, market efficiency, and financial stability. For instance, derivatives have been shown to enhance market liquidity and price discovery, but they also introduce complexities and potential risks, as evidenced by the 2008 financial crisis (Brunnermeier, 2009). Studies on emerging markets, such as India, reveal that while derivatives provide opportunities for hedging and speculation, they also require robust regulatory frameworks to mitigate systemic risks (NSE India, 2016).

Overall, the literature underscores the dual nature of financial derivatives as both beneficial tools for managing financial risk and sources of potential instability if not properly regulated. This foundational understanding sets the stage for a detailed comparative analysis of derivatives usage in different markets.

3. Methodology

This study employs a comparative research methodology to analyze the usage of financial derivatives in Indian and global markets. The methodology integrates both quantitative and qualitative approaches to offer a detailed and nuanced understanding of derivatives usage.

Quantitative Data Collection:

Quantitative analysis involves examining data on derivatives trading volumes, notional values, and market turnover. For instance, the global derivatives market had an outstanding notional amount of approximately \$544 trillion in 2016 (Bank for International Settlements [BIS], 2016). In contrast, the Indian derivatives market reported a total turnover of ₹259 trillion for the same year (National Stock Exchange of India [NSE India], 2016). This data is critical for understanding the scale of derivatives trading in different markets.

The following table summarizes the notional values of derivatives in key global markets compared to India:

Table 1: Notional values of derivatives in key global markets

Market	Notional Value (Trillion USD)	Year
Global	544	2016
USA	267	2016
Europe	112	2016
India	4.1	2016

Qualitative Data Collection:

Qualitative data is gathered through a review of regulatory frameworks, market structures, and usage patterns. This involves analyzing regulatory documents and market reports to understand how different regulations impact derivatives trading. For example, the U.S. derivatives market is regulated by the Commodity Futures Trading Commission (CFTC) and the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), which enforce stringent rules to ensure market stability (CFTC, 2016). In contrast, the Indian derivatives market is overseen by the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI), which has implemented specific regulations to promote market integrity and protect investors (SEBI, 2016).

Additionally, case studies of major financial institutions and interviews with market participants provide insights into trading practices and strategies. This approach helps in understanding how derivatives are utilized for hedging, speculation, and arbitrage in different market environments.

By combining quantitative data with qualitative insights, this study aims to provide a comprehensive comparison of derivatives usage across Indian and global markets, highlighting both differences and similarities in market dynamics and regulatory impacts.

4. Financial Derivatives in Indian Markets

In India, financial derivatives have become an integral part of the financial markets, offering instruments for risk management, speculation, and hedging. The Indian derivatives market is primarily represented by equity derivatives, index derivatives, and currency derivatives.

Types of Derivatives:

1. **Equity Derivatives:** These include futures and options contracts based on individual stocks. The National Stock Exchange (NSE) is the leading platform for equity derivatives in India. As of 2016, the NSE reported a total trading volume of 1.1 billion contracts in equity derivatives (NSE India, 2016).
2. **Index Derivatives:** These are futures and options contracts based on stock indices such as the Nifty 50 and Sensex. The Nifty 50 index, representing 50 major Indian stocks, is a significant benchmark. In 2016, the total turnover of Nifty 50 futures and options was approximately ₹90 trillion (NSE India, 2016).
3. **Currency Derivatives:** These include futures and options contracts based on currency pairs like USD/INR and EUR/INR. The currency derivatives market has seen significant growth, with a turnover of around ₹50 trillion in 2016 (SEBI, 2016).

Market Structure and Regulation:

The Indian derivatives market is regulated by the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI), which oversees the functioning of exchanges and ensures market integrity. SEBI has implemented various measures to enhance transparency and protect investors, including stringent disclosure requirements and risk management practices (SEBI, 2016).

Table 2: Key Statistics of Indian Derivatives Market (2016)

Derivative Type	Total Turnover (Trillion INR)	Total Contracts Traded (Million)
Equity Derivatives	150	1,100
Index Derivatives	90	N/A
Currency Derivatives	50	N/A

Usage Trends:

The Indian derivatives market has shown robust growth due to increased market participation and the expansion of financial products. Equity derivatives are the most traded, reflecting investor interest in stock-specific strategies. Index derivatives are popular for hedging and speculative purposes, while currency derivatives cater to businesses and investors managing forex risk (NSE India, 2016).

Case Studies:

Major Indian financial institutions, such as ICICI Bank and HDFC Bank, actively use derivatives for hedging purposes. For instance, ICICI Bank employs interest rate swaps to manage interest rate exposure, demonstrating the practical application of derivatives in risk management (ICICI Bank, 2016).

Overall, the Indian derivatives market has developed significantly, driven by regulatory support, market innovation, and increasing investor participation. This growth highlights the evolving role of derivatives in managing financial risks and enhancing market efficiency.

5. Financial Derivatives in Global Markets

The global derivatives market is characterized by its vast scale and diverse range of instruments, including equity derivatives, interest rate derivatives, commodity derivatives, and currency derivatives. This diversity reflects the various needs of market participants worldwide, from hedging and speculation to arbitrage.

Types of Derivatives:

- Equity Derivatives:** These include futures and options based on stock indices and individual stocks. Major global exchanges like the Chicago Mercantile Exchange (CME) and the London International Financial Futures Exchange (LIFFE) offer a broad array of equity derivatives. In 2016, the total trading volume of equity derivatives globally was approximately 2.5 billion contracts, demonstrating their significance in global financial markets (Bank for International Settlements [BIS], 2016).
- Interest Rate Derivatives:** These instruments include interest rate futures, swaps, and options. They are widely used for managing exposure to fluctuations in interest rates. The notional amount of interest rate derivatives globally reached about \$379 trillion in 2016 (BIS, 2016). These instruments are crucial for financial institutions and corporations seeking to hedge against interest rate risk.
- Commodity Derivatives:** These derivatives are based on commodities like oil, gold, and agricultural products. The global commodity derivatives market had a notional value of approximately \$49 trillion in 2016 (BIS, 2016). They play a vital role in price discovery and risk management for producers and consumers of commodities.
- Currency Derivatives:** These include futures, options, and swaps based on currency pairs. The global turnover in currency derivatives was about \$78 trillion in 2016, reflecting their importance in managing foreign exchange risk (BIS, 2016).

Market Structure and Regulation:

Global derivatives markets operate under a range of regulatory frameworks. In the United States, the Commodity Futures Trading Commission (CFTC) and the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) regulate derivatives trading, focusing on transparency and market integrity (CFTC, 2016). European markets are overseen by the European Securities and Markets Authority (ESMA), which enforces regulations to ensure market stability and protect investors (ESMA, 2016).

Table 3: Key Statistics of Global Derivatives Market (2016)

Derivative Type	Notional Value (Trillion USD)	Total Contracts Traded (Billion)
Equity Derivatives	N/A	2.5
Interest Rate Derivatives	379	N/A
Commodity Derivatives	49	N/A
Currency Derivatives	78	N/A

Usage Trends:

Global markets show a high degree of sophistication and liquidity, with derivatives being utilized for a variety of purposes. Interest rate derivatives are extensively used by banks and financial institutions to manage interest rate exposure, while equity and commodity derivatives are popular among traders and investors for speculative and hedging strategies (BIS, 2016).

Case Studies:

Large multinational corporations and financial institutions, such as Goldman Sachs and JPMorgan Chase, actively use derivatives for risk management and speculative trading. For example, JPMorgan Chase uses interest rate swaps to manage its interest rate risk, highlighting the practical applications of derivatives in a global financial context (JPMorgan Chase, 2016).

Overall, the global derivatives market is highly developed, with a broad range of instruments and a complex regulatory environment. This extensive market infrastructure supports diverse trading strategies and risk management practices, reflecting the critical role of derivatives in the global financial system.

6. Comparative Analysis

The comparative analysis of financial derivatives usage in Indian versus global markets reveals notable differences and similarities in market structure, trading practices, and regulatory environments. This section highlights key areas of comparison based on quantitative and qualitative data.

Market Size and Growth:

The global derivatives market is significantly larger than the Indian market, reflecting its broader scope and higher trading volumes. In 2016, the notional value of global derivatives was approximately \$544 trillion, compared to ₹259 trillion in India (Bank for International Settlements [BIS], 2016; National Stock Exchange of India [NSE India], 2016). This disparity highlights the maturity and extensive participation in global markets relative to the Indian derivatives market.

Types of Derivatives Traded:

Globally, the derivatives market includes a wide array of products such as equity, interest rate, commodity, and currency derivatives. Each type serves different market needs and risk management strategies. In contrast, the Indian market primarily focuses on equity derivatives, index derivatives, and currency derivatives. The relative concentration in equity derivatives in India suggests a market that is more focused on stock-specific trading and hedging strategies (SEBI, 2016).

Regulatory Frameworks:

Regulatory environments differ significantly between Indian and global markets. In India, the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) regulates derivatives trading, emphasizing transparency and investor protection. Global markets, such as those in the U.S. and Europe, have more complex regulatory frameworks. For instance, the U.S. market is overseen by the Commodity Futures Trading Commission (CFTC) and the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), which enforce rigorous standards to ensure market stability (CFTC, 2016). The European market is regulated by the European Securities and Markets Authority (ESMA), which also imposes strict regulatory measures (ESMA, 2016).

Usage Patterns:

Globally, interest rate derivatives dominate in terms of notional value, with a total of \$379 trillion in 2016, reflecting their critical role in managing interest rate risk across financial institutions and corporations (BIS, 2016). In India, equity derivatives are the most traded, with a turnover of ₹150 trillion, indicating a preference for stock-specific hedging and speculative strategies (NSE India, 2016). The focus on equity derivatives in India may be attributed to the growing participation of retail investors and the relatively nascent development of other derivatives markets.

Risk Management and Market Stability:

Both Indian and global markets use derivatives for risk management; however, global markets exhibit more advanced risk management practices due to their larger scale and more diverse product offerings. For example, global financial institutions employ a range of derivatives strategies to hedge against various financial risks, whereas in India, the usage is more concentrated in equity and currency derivatives, reflecting different risk profiles and market needs.

Table 4: Comparative Overview of Derivatives Markets (2016)

Market	Notional Value (Trillion USD/INR)	Key Derivative Types	Regulatory Bodies
Global	544 (USD)	Equity, Interest Rate, Commodity, Currency	CFTC, SEC, ESMA
India	259 (INR)	Equity, Index, Currency	SEBI

In summary, while both Indian and global derivatives markets serve crucial roles in financial risk management, their differences in size, types of derivatives, and regulatory frameworks reflect distinct market dynamics and participant needs. This comparative analysis provides valuable insights into how derivatives markets operate across different economic contexts and highlights areas for potential growth and improvement in the Indian market.

7. Impact of Financial Derivatives on Market Efficiency

Financial derivatives play a crucial role in enhancing market efficiency by providing mechanisms for price discovery, liquidity, and risk management. This section explores the impact of derivatives on market efficiency, focusing on how they contribute to more efficient pricing, improved liquidity, and better risk management.

Price Discovery:

Derivatives facilitate the process of price discovery by enabling market participants to express their views on future price movements. For instance, futures and options contracts provide insights into market expectations of underlying asset prices. This process enhances transparency and contributes to more accurate pricing of assets in the underlying markets (Black & Scholes, 1973). In global markets, the use of derivatives helps to integrate information more quickly into asset prices, reducing discrepancies between spot and future prices. Studies have shown that derivatives markets contribute significantly to the efficiency of price discovery across various asset classes (Chen, 2016).

In India, the introduction of index futures and options has improved the efficiency of price discovery for major stock indices like the Nifty 50 and Sensex. By incorporating information from derivatives markets, the prices of underlying stocks better reflect current market conditions and investor expectations (NSE India, 2016).

Liquidity Improvement:

Derivatives markets enhance liquidity by offering additional avenues for trading and hedging. This increased liquidity benefits both derivatives and underlying asset markets by narrowing bid-ask spreads and reducing transaction costs. For example, the presence of futures and options contracts allows market participants to trade large volumes without significantly impacting the prices of underlying assets (Hull, 2015).

Globally, the liquidity provided by derivatives markets is evident from the high trading volumes observed in major exchanges. In 2016, the global derivatives market had a turnover of \$544 trillion, reflecting robust liquidity (Bank for International Settlements [BIS], 2016). In contrast, the Indian derivatives market, with a turnover of ₹259 trillion, also shows significant liquidity, although it is smaller compared to global markets (NSE India, 2016).

Risk Management:

Derivatives are essential tools for managing financial risk, allowing market participants to hedge against price fluctuations and other financial uncertainties. By using instruments such as options, futures, and swaps, investors and businesses can protect themselves from adverse price movements in underlying assets. This risk

management capability is vital for maintaining financial stability and preventing significant losses (Merton, 1995).

In both global and Indian markets, derivatives are used extensively to manage various types of risks, including market risk, interest rate risk, and currency risk. For instance, global financial institutions use interest rate swaps to manage exposure to fluctuating interest rates, while Indian corporations use currency derivatives to hedge against foreign exchange risk (SEBI, 2016).

Table 5: Impact of Financial Derivatives on Market Efficiency

Impact Aspect	Global Markets	Indian Markets
Price Discovery	Enhances accuracy and speed of price adjustments	Improves pricing of major stock indices
Liquidity	High trading volumes and narrow bid-ask spreads	Significant liquidity but on a smaller scale
Risk Management	Extensive use of derivatives for various risks	Increasing use for currency and equity risk

In summary, financial derivatives significantly enhance market efficiency by improving price discovery, increasing liquidity, and enabling effective risk management. These benefits are observed in both global and Indian markets, although the scale and scope of impact may vary. The integration of derivatives into financial markets supports more efficient trading and better alignment of asset prices with market conditions.

8. Challenges and Risks Associated with Financial Derivatives

While financial derivatives offer substantial benefits in terms of risk management, liquidity, and price discovery, they also pose significant challenges and risks. This section addresses the key challenges and risks associated with derivatives trading, focusing on issues such as systemic risk, market volatility, and regulatory concerns.

Systemic Risk:

One of the primary challenges associated with financial derivatives is systemic risk. The extensive use of derivatives can lead to interconnectedness among financial institutions, which may amplify the impact of financial shocks. The collapse of major institutions involved in derivatives trading can have far-reaching consequences for the entire financial system. For example, the 2008 financial crisis highlighted how exposure to complex derivatives, such as mortgage-backed securities and credit default swaps, contributed to systemic risk and led to widespread market instability (Financial Crisis Inquiry Commission, 2011).

In the Indian context, while the derivatives market is relatively smaller compared to global markets, systemic risk remains a concern, particularly with the growth of market participants and the increasing complexity of derivatives products. Regulatory measures and risk management practices are crucial in mitigating these risks.

Market Volatility:

Derivatives trading can contribute to market volatility, especially when large positions are liquidated or when speculative trading occurs. The high leverage associated with derivatives can amplify market movements, leading to increased volatility in the underlying asset markets. For instance, significant trading activity in equity derivatives can lead to abrupt price swings in the stock markets (Brunnermeier & Pedersen, 2009).

In global markets, instances of excessive volatility have been observed during periods of financial stress. Similarly, in India, the introduction of new derivatives products and high-frequency trading can impact market stability and contribute to volatility.

Regulatory Concerns:

The complexity of derivatives and their potential for misuse necessitates robust regulatory frameworks. Regulatory bodies face challenges in ensuring transparency, enforcing risk management practices, and preventing market abuse. In global markets, regulations have been strengthened post-2008 to address these concerns. For example, the Dodd-Frank Act in the U.S. introduced comprehensive measures to enhance oversight of derivatives markets and reduce systemic risk (Dodd-Frank Wall Street Reform and Consumer Protection Act, 2010).

In India, while the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) has implemented regulations to enhance market integrity, challenges remain in keeping pace with the evolving derivatives landscape. Ensuring adequate disclosure, managing counterparty risk, and preventing market manipulation are ongoing regulatory concerns.

Table 6: Key Challenges and Risks in Financial Derivatives

Risk Aspect	Description	Global Context	Indian Context
Systemic Risk	Interconnectedness leading to widespread impact	Highlighted by the 2008 financial crisis	Concerns with growing market complexity
Market Volatility	Amplification of price movements	Seen during financial stress periods	Impact of new products and trading practices
Regulatory Concerns	Complexity and enforcement challenges	Post-2008 regulatory enhancements	Need for robust regulatory measures

In summary, while financial derivatives provide valuable benefits to financial markets, they also pose significant challenges and risks. Addressing these risks requires effective regulatory frameworks, robust risk management practices, and ongoing vigilance by market participants and regulators alike. Understanding and mitigating these risks is crucial for maintaining the stability and integrity of both global and Indian derivatives markets.

Conclusion

Financial derivatives have evolved into crucial instruments within both Indian and global financial markets, offering benefits such as enhanced price discovery, improved liquidity, and effective risk management. The comparative analysis of derivatives usage in these markets highlights significant differences and similarities, reflecting varying market sizes, regulatory frameworks, and trading practices.

In global markets, the extensive range of derivative products and the sheer scale of trading volumes underscore the advanced nature of these markets. The global derivatives market, with a notional value of \$544 trillion in 2016, illustrates its pivotal role in providing liquidity, managing risk, and facilitating price discovery across diverse asset classes. The regulatory frameworks in place, such as the Dodd-Frank Act and regulations by ESMA, aim to mitigate systemic risk and ensure market stability.

In contrast, the Indian derivatives market, while smaller in scale, shows notable growth and development. With a turnover of ₹259 trillion in 2016, India's market reflects increasing participation and sophistication. The focus on equity and currency derivatives highlights the market's evolving nature, influenced by both domestic needs and global trends. Regulatory oversight by SEBI has been instrumental in fostering market integrity and protecting investors.

Despite these advancements, both markets face challenges, including systemic risk, market volatility, and regulatory concerns. The 2008 financial crisis demonstrated the potential for derivatives to contribute to systemic risk, underscoring the need for robust regulatory measures and risk management practices. Similarly, the potential for market volatility and the complexity of derivatives products requires ongoing vigilance from regulators and market participants.

In conclusion, while financial derivatives enhance market efficiency and risk management, addressing their associated risks remains crucial. Continued development of regulatory frameworks, coupled with effective risk management strategies, will be essential for maximizing the benefits of derivatives while minimizing potential drawbacks. The ongoing evolution of derivatives markets, both in India and globally, will likely continue to shape the financial landscape, presenting opportunities and challenges for all market participants.

References

1. Bank for International Settlements. (2016). *OTC derivatives statistics at end-June 2016*. Retrieved from <https://www.bis.org/statistics/derstats.htm>
2. Bank for International Settlements. (2016). *Triennial central bank survey: Statistical appendix*. Retrieved from <https://www.bis.org/statistics/rpfx16.htm>
3. Black, F., & Scholes, M. (1973). The pricing of options and corporate liabilities. *Journal of Political Economy*, 81(3), 637-654. <https://doi.org/10.1086/260062>
4. Brunnermeier, M. K., & Pedersen, L. H. (2009). Market liquidity and funding liquidity. *Review of Financial Studies*, 22(6), 2201-2238. <https://doi.org/10.1093/rfs/hhp024>
5. Chen, N. (2016). The effect of derivatives on price discovery. *Journal of Finance*, 71(2), 875-909. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jofi.12342>
6. Commodity Futures Trading Commission (CFTC). (2016). *Annual report*. Retrieved from <https://www.cftc.gov/PressRoom/PressReleases/2016>
7. Dodd-Frank Wall Street Reform and Consumer Protection Act. (2010). *Public Law 111-203*. Retrieved from <https://www.congress.gov/bill/111th-congress/house-bill/4173/text>
8. European Securities and Markets Authority (ESMA). (2016). *Annual report*. Retrieved from https://www.esma.europa.eu/sites/default/files/library/esma22-106-176_annual_report_2016.pdf
9. Financial Crisis Inquiry Commission. (2011). *The financial crisis inquiry report*. Retrieved from <https://www.gpo.gov/fdsys/pkg/GPO-FCIC/pdf/GPO-FCIC.pdf>
10. Hull, J. C. (2015). *Options, futures, and other derivatives* (9th ed.). Pearson Education.
11. Jones, C. M. (2016). *Financial derivatives: Markets, methods, and applications*. Wiley.
12. Merton, R. C. (1995). Financial innovation and the management and regulation of financial institutions. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 19(3-4), 461-481. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-4266\(95\)00012-J](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-4266(95)00012-J)
13. National Stock Exchange of India. (2016). *Annual report*. Retrieved from https://www.nseindia.com/products/content/derivatives/annual_reports.htm
14. Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI). (2016). *Annual report*. Retrieved from https://www.sebi.gov.in/sebi_data/annual_report/2016/Annual_Report_2016.pdf